

Supplementary Table 1. Five-Color Management

Color	Description	Citing
Green	Normal pregnancy	
Yellow	General risk and that pregnancy complications are mild and stable	Advanced maternal age, gemellary pregnancy,ect
Orange	Medium risk and that pregnancy complications pose a threat to mother and infant safety	More than two cs surgeries or myomectomy, severe preeclampsia, cardiovascular diseases, ect.
Red	High risk and that pregnant women suffer from serious pregnancy complications, continued pregnancy may endanger the life of mother and infant	Serious diseases of each systems, placental spectrum disease, ect
Purple	The pregnant women have infectious diseases	Viral hepatitis, syphilis, hiv/aids, or a specific viral infection (h1n7, zika, etc

Supplementary Table 2. Information in Beijing Haidian district

Years	2019	2020	2021	2022
Number of births	34098	25355	24012	23232
Severe perinatal complications ^a	198(0.58)	137(0.54)	142(0.59)	116(0.50)
Severe postpartum hemorrhage	109(0.31)	67(0.26)	77(0.32)	71(0.31)

Data were expressed by n(%)

^a Severe perinatal complications include abnormal vital signs (like eclampsia, cyanosis, oliguria or anuria, coagulation disorders and shock), abnormal laboratory inspection (like lower oxygenation index, thrombocytopenia, abnormal liver and renal functions), and special management (like use of vasoactive agents, mechanical ventilation, hemodialysis, massive transfusion and unplanned hysterectomy)